

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii), $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of metal complex-ion equilibria. The pK_1^H of the ligand and $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ of the complexes of Y^{3+} , La^{3+} , Nd^{3+} and Gd^{3+} were evaluated by the half integral method. In the case of dysprosium and praseodymium metal systems, the differences between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were found to be less than 1.78 log units and hence the same were evaluated by the least square method. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability of various metal chelates was found to be $Y^{3+} > Gd^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > La^{3+} > Pr^{3+} > Dy^{3+}$.

An attempt to interpret the stability data in terms of an entirely ionic type of bonding in these complexes was unsuccessful as the plot of Z^2/r vs $\log K_1$ values was not linear. The possibility of covalent interaction, however, cannot be completely excluded, as reported in the case of acetylacetonate chelates of rare earths⁸. The probable explanation of non-linearity could be that the assumption about ionic character of the metal-ligand bond, on which the linearity relation is based, is not valid. Other probable causes could be possibilities of higher coordination number of metal ion and steric factors.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES OF 2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHALIDENE-4'-CHLORO-2'-METHOXYANILINE WITH SOME TRIVALENT LANTHANIDES

Cations	$t = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ$						
	H^+	Y^{3+}	La^{3+}	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}	Gd^{3+}
$\log K_1$	9.40	9.23	8.72	8.20	9.05	7.59	9.07
$\log K_2$	—	7.08	6.10	6.73	7.05	6.28	6.78

For proton association (H^+), K_1 corresponds to the species LH ; while for metal ions, K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species ML_1 and ML_2 , respectively.

The standard deviation ranged from 0.05 to 0.1; the limits of error were ± 0.06 .

Acknowledgement

The authors record their sincere thanks to Dr. D. G. Vartak, B. A. R. C., Bombay, for valuable suggestions.

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Polarographic Reduction of Uranyl(II) in Presence of Some Disubstituted Pyridines

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Manuscript received 27 July 1981, accepted 2 February 1982

THE present paper describes the polarographic reduction of uranyl(II) in presence of some disubstituted pyridines, viz., 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DPH), 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP) and 3-hydroxypyridine-2-thiol (HPT). All the systems show diffusion controlled irreversible reduction waves. Kinetic parameters (αn and $k_{1/2}$) have been calculated and discussed. The ligands contain ideal sites for formation of sterically favoured five-membered ring and provide scope for comparison of donor properties of -OH, -NH₂ and -SH groups. Reactions of $UO_2(II)$ with these ligands have been studied earlier pH -metrically¹⁻⁵ wherein metal-ligand stability constants were determined.

Experimental

A D.C. manual polarograph with a scalamp galvanometer was used in all investigations. All potential measurements were made with reference to a saturated calomel electrode. The dropping mercury electrode had the characteristics, $m^{2/3} \cdot t^{1/6} = 2.054 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$, $h = 40 \text{ cm}$, $t = 3.8 \text{ sec}$. Purified nitrogen was passed through each solution to remove dissolved oxygen. All measurements were carried out at room temperature ($30 \pm 0.1^\circ$).

Reagent grade chemicals were used. Solution of uranyl nitrate was prepared in double distilled water. Stock solutions of DPH and AHP (Aldrich Chemical Co., U.S.A.) were prepared in double distilled water and that of HPT (Fluka AG, Switzerland) in purified methanol. While $UO_2(II)$ -DHP and $UO_2(II)$ -AHP systems were studied in aqueous media, $UO_2(II)$ -HPT system was studied in 30% methanol medium owing to the limited solubility of the ligand in water. Sodium perchlorate was used as the supporting electrolyte and ionic strength was kept constant ($\mu = 0.1$). Acetate buffer was used to maintain the pH . Gelatin (0.003%) was used as the maxima suppressor.

Results and Discussion

Well defined single cathodic waves were obtained in all the three cases. $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ values ($69 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$) show irreversible nature of the systems and constant values of $i_d / (h_{eff})^{1/2}$ show that the waves are diffusion controlled. Kinetic parameters have been calculated using Oldham and Parry method⁶. According to these authors the equation for an irreversible diffusion controlled wave (at 30°) is

$$-E_{de} = -E_{1/2} + \frac{0.060}{\alpha n} \log \left[\frac{x(5.5-x)}{5(1-x)} \right] \quad \dots (1)$$

where $x = \frac{i_E}{i_{lim}}$, i_E = current at potential E which is valid in the entire region $0 < x < 1$. The plots of E_{a_e} vs $\log \left[\frac{x(5.5-x)}{5(1-x)} \right]$ yield the values of $\frac{0.060}{\alpha n}$ (slope) and $-E_{\frac{1}{2}}$ (intercept). Also, for an irreversible wave the half wave potential is related to the rate constant for the electrode reduction by the expression,

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = E_0 + \frac{0.060}{\alpha n} \log \left[0.89 k_{f,h}^0 \sqrt{t/D} \right] \quad \dots (2)$$

where $k_{f,h}^0$ is the formal rate constant at a reference potential $E_0 = -0.2412$ volts vs S.C.E. and D and t have their usual significance. The reference potential in the present investigations has been chosen as the normal hydrogen electrode potential (-0.2412 volts vs S.C.E.) and the values of $D^{\frac{1}{2}}$ have been obtained using Ilkovic equation. Values of αn and $k_{f,h}^0$ have been calculated and presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS

ligand conc. (mM)	[UO ₂ ²⁺] = 1 × 10 ⁻⁴ M			
	-E _{1/2} (volts vs SCE)	αn	D ^{1/2} × 10 ³ (cm sec ⁻²)	k _{f,h} ⁰ × 10 ⁶ (cm ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹)
(a) System : UO ₂ (II)-DHP, pH = 4.4				
2.0	0.460	0.750	2.33	2.71
4.0	0.480	0.742	2.19	1.54
6.0	0.488	0.740	2.03	1.16
8.0	0.492	0.739	1.95	1.01
(b) System : UO ₂ (II)-AHP, pH = 4.4				
2.0	0.455	0.752	2.41	3.19
4.0	0.476	0.749	2.34	1.52
6.0	0.485	0.752	2.16	1.20
8.0	0.490	0.747	2.17	1.10
(c) System : UO ₂ (II)-HPT, pH = 4.6				
2.0	0.463	0.747	2.18	1.74
4.0	0.481	0.741	2.11	1.46
6.0	0.490	0.740	2.03	1.10
8.0	0.493	0.740	1.86	1.02

A perusal of the results show that the $k_{f,h}^0$ values for reduction of UO₂²⁺ in presence of the same concentration of the ligands follow the order HPT < DHP < AHP. Since higher value of the rate constant signifies easier reduction and hence lower stability of the complex, the order of the strength of the metal ligand bond in the complexes of the three ligands appears to be HPT > DHP > AHP.

Uranyl ion falls in the category of hard acids (class 'a') for which the strength of the metal ligand bond should follow the O > N > S order of the donor atoms, so that the order of stability of the complexes formed with the three ligands under study should be DHP > AHP > HPT. For DHP and AHP, the studies were made under similar conditions (both in aqueous media) and the observed behaviour is as expected from theoretical considerations. Deviation in the behaviour of HPT may be because the study was made in 30% methanol medium which has a dielectric constant lower than that of water.

Vlcek⁵ also approximated that a complex with a nonhomogeneous coordination sphere will be reduced more easily (i.e., the rate constant for reduction will be higher) than one with fully homogeneous coordination sphere. Consistent with the above, the rate constant for the reduction of the AHP complex is higher than that for the reduction of the DHP complex.

Acknowledgement

Grateful thanks of the authors are due to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for the award of a Research Fellowship to one of them (R. S. S.).

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Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-Sulphamethoxazole Complexes with Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Mg²⁺

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Manuscript received 31 July 1981, accepted 7 June 1982

In the present investigation, potentiometric studies have been carried out on 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphamethoxazole and its complexes with some bivalent metal ions. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) of the reagent and the formation constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of its metal chelates have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphamethoxazole was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and the amine in alcohol-DMF mixture and was repeatedly crystallised to get an analytically pure compound, m.p. 240° (observed). All the metal perchlorates used were prepared from metal salts and perchloric acid both of A. R. grade. These were standardised complexometrically by EDTA titrations². Other experimental details were the same as in our earlier communication³.

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned here that the ligand does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental